

Implementation of New Education Policy on the Higher Education and its Opportunities

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Abstract

A holistic and multidisciplinary education would attempt to integrate the development of all human capacities - intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral. In the long run, such a comprehensive education will be the approach of all undergraduate programmes, including those in professional, technical, and vocational fields. Even engineering schools, such as IITs, will shift toward more holistic and multidisciplinary education that includes more arts and humanities. Students of the arts and humanities will strive to learn more science, and all will strive to include more vocational topics and soft skills. This paper will cover all the opportunities that can be achieved through the New Education Policy 2020. This paper also contains the highlights of the policy. Curricular structures that are imaginative and adaptable will allow for creative combinations of subjects to be studied, as well as many entry and departure points. The aim is to comprise all the good aspects of the policy which will be very beneficial for the upcoming generation education practices. The paper is also holds the educational preparation of the teaching fraternity to look beyond the ancient method of teaching and need to be prepared for the forthcoming generation teaching methods.

Keywords: - New Education Policy, Holistic development, Multidisciplinary education, Higher education, Opportunities in NEP.

Introduction

The minister of human resource management has altered the old education policy. This move was made to improve education under the chairmanship of ISRO Chief Doctor K Kasturirangan. The union cabinet of India approved the national education strategy on July 29, 2020. It superseded India's previous educational strategy, enacted in 1986. This policy has a significant positive impact on Indian education. Students can select a language based on their interests. The National Education Policy will make education available to all students from preschool to secondary school. The aim is to paving the way for radical reform in the school and higher education systems. The name has been changed MHRD to Ministry of

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Education. Following the old national education policy, which was established in 1986, this is the first education policy of the twenty-first century, replacing a 34-year-old education policy.

Higher education in India is undergoing a transformation, with the National Education Policy 2020 introducing multi-faceted changes ranging from the regulatory framework to curriculum structure and research environment. First and foremost, the long-awaited National Education Policy (NEP) announcement has cleared the way for the establishment of a single regulating agency for the country's higher education. The regulatory body, to be known as the Higher Education Commission of India (HECI), will serve as the only authority for all public and private educational institutions in the country (except those involved in medical and law education). In addition, a National Research Foundation would be established to oversee all research efforts carried out by the country's numerous academic institutions.

The new NEP is built on four pillars: accessibility, equity, quality, and accountability. The original 10+2 structure will be replaced by a 5+3+3+4 framework that includes 12 years of education and 3 years of Anganwadi/pre-school.

Objectives of the study:-

- The primary objective of this research is to study the impact of New Education Policy 2020 on higher education.
- The study also outlines the salient features of NEP and analyses how they affect the existing education system.

Research Methodology

- Research methodology this research is a descriptive study .The necessary secondary data was collected from various websites including those of Government of India, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analysed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

Scope of the study

The study will be beneficial for the institution's curriculum and pedagogy must foster a strong feeling of respect for fundamental duties and Constitutional principles, a sense of belonging to one's country, and a conscious understanding of one's tasks and responsibilities in a changing world. The scope is to make available advance knowledge, skills, beliefs, and dispositions that enable responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living, and global well-being, reflecting a genuinely global citizen.

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Highlights of the New Education Policy

- All higher education establishments, with the exception of medical and law schools, will be overseen by a single regulator.
- MPhil. Classes are being discontinued.
- Implemented application and knowledge-based board examinations.
- The same standards will apply to both public and private higher education institutions.
- Teaching in one's mother tongue or a regional language has been made mandatory until the fifth grade.
- Common admission examinations for colleges and universities.
- The educational curriculum should place a greater emphasis on core principles.
- Vocational education will begin in the sixth grade.
- The 10+2 study culture will be discontinued, and a new structure of 5+3+3+4 will be implemented, with age groups of 3-8, 8-11, 11-14, and 14-18 years.
- Board Exams on up to two occasions throughout any given school year, one for the main examination and one for improvement, if needed.
- PARAKH, a new National Assessment Centre, is being established (Performance Assessment, Review, and Analysis of Knowledge for Holistic Development)
- Education that is equitable and inclusive focuses on socially and economically disadvantaged groups (SEDGs)
- A special budget for gender inclusion, as well as Special Education Zones for underserved regions and groups
- Strong and transparent methods for teacher recruitment, as well as merit-based performance
- Providing access to all resources through school complexes and clusters
- Establishment of a State School Standards Authority (SSSA)
- vocational education in the school and higher education systems
- Raising the GER in higher education to 50%

Education that is holistic and multidisciplinary, with various entry/exit points NEP 2020 Higher Education. The NEP 2020 was designed to increase the Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) in higher education from 26 percent to 50 percent by 2030. It strives to develop students' whole personalities by improving infrastructure for open and distance learning, online education, and boosting the use of technology in education. Furthermore, the National Research Foundation (NRF) will be established to promote research throughout the country. A National Accreditation Council (NAC) would be established as a single regulator for higher education institutions across the country. To fulfil numerous functions, the Higher Education Council of India (HECI) would have multiple verticals.

Higher Education in the NEP 2020 The NEP 2020 aimed to raise the Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) in higher education from 26% to 50% by 2030. It aims to develop students' entire personalities by enhancing the infrastructure for open and distance learning, online education, and increasing the use of technology in education. In addition, the National Research

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Foundation (NRF) would be formed to foster research across the country. As a single regulator for higher education institutions across the country, a National Accreditation Council (NAC) will be established. The Higher Education Council of India (HECI) would have multiple verticals to fulfil various functions.

Higher Education Accreditation

Among other crucial functions, higher education regulatory systems would include "accreditation" by an impartial agency. Institutions will be able to provide Open Distance Learning (ODL) and online programmes if they are accredited to do so in order to expand their offerings, improve access, raise GER, and create chances for lifelong learning.

The National Accreditation Board for Education and Training (NABET), Quality Council of India (QCI) and the Department of Industrial Promotion and Internal Trade (DPIIT), Ministry of Commerce and Industries, Government of India developed an accreditation scheme to improve the credibility of Learning Service Providers (LSP). Accreditation ensures the quality of the trainer/faculty, the infrastructure, the programme design (development and delivery), and the Training Management System (3 Dimensions: Hardware, Software, Humanware / Skinware).

Cyber security education and expertise

According to the World Economic Forum's (WEF) 2021 Global Risk Report, 'Cyber Security Failure' is the world's fourth most serious hazard. Due to the increasing epidemic, education and learning have already moved to cyberspace, making it critical to preserve each individual's privacy and security. As digitisation becomes more prevalent, it is critical to ensure the security of our networks and cyberspace. In this current environment, it is critical that capacity building for 'Cyber Security Resilience' is prioritised and included in all higher education curricula, regardless of field of study.

Higher Education Research and Innovation

One of NEP 2020's primary focus areas is to stimulate strong R&D investments from both the public and commercial sectors. This will foster innovation and new thinking. To assist this, there is a strong industry commitment and tight collaboration with academia for industry-led skilling, up skilling, and reskilling. Furthermore, it is necessary to instil skill sets for driving understanding about "Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)" and its protection in order to reap benefits from it.

The National Forum on Educational Technology (NETF)

The establishment of a NETF under NEP 2020 is a step in the right direction. Hosting Quality Ed-Tech tools across all dimensions of teaching-learning delivery would allow learning institutions to change swiftly. The emphasis should be on hosting indigenous Ed-Tech tools on "open-source development platforms" with built-in cyber security resilience to ensure "privacy and security," in addition to adhering to cyber security standards, the use of

firewalls, and the use of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) to protect against external threats and vulnerabilities. This will protect individual students' "personal privacy."

Findings

The New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 of India proposes numerous improvements in higher education. One among them is the launch of a four-year undergraduate programme beginning next year. Delhi University, India's largest university has authorised it. The NEP, if adopted in letter and spirit, has the potential to transform the classroom experience. Higher education in India used to generate disciplinary experts, but the NEP 2020 wants to reverse that. B.Tech students will now study a few of social science disciplines in addition to their engineering branch. As a result, engineering degree programmes will include certain arts and humanities subjects. Students of social sciences will also study additional science disciplines. As a result, all degree programmes will include occupational subjects as well as soft skill development.

Conclusion

The Government of India wishes to promote Indian languages, arts, and culture via education, which is emphasised in the NEP 2020. The regional language or mother tongue, as well as the local dialect, are used as the medium of instruction at higher education institutions. The NEP 2020 stipulates that students who are not proficient in English will be encouraged to pursue additional studies in regional languages, which will help raise the gross enrolment ratio (GER) in higher education. The National Testing Agency would administer a single university entrance exam, according to the NEP 2020.

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